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Assessment of coastal vulnerability to sea level rise: a case study of the Kenyan coastline

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Introduction: Kenya's 640 km coastline faces escalating exposure to sea-level rise, yet no integrated, spatially explicit assessment combining physical and socioeconomic vulnerability exists for the entire national coastline. This study addresses that gap by developing the first GIS-based Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) at national scale using exclusively open-access data.

Methods: The shoreline was divided into 7,555 segments of approximately 200 m, each attributed with eight physical indicators (including shoreline change rate, coastal elevation, geomorphology, bathymetry, and sea-level rise trend) and three socioeconomic indicators (population density, land use/land cover, and distance to coastal infrastructure). Indicators were ranked on a 1–5 ordinal scale and weighted using the Analytical Hierarchy Process (CR = 0.046 and 0.033 for physical and socioeconomic sets respectively), then aggregated into a Physical Vulnerability Index (PVI) and Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index (SoVI), each normalised to a 0–100 scale and combined into the final CVI.

Results: Overall, 31.7% of coastal segments fall in the High or Very High CVI class (mean CVI = 51.66). The most vulnerable stretches are concentrated along the Kilifi–Malindi corridor, where active erosion and sandy geomorphology coincide with elevated socioeconomic exposure, and near the Mombasa urban core. An at-risk inventory of 46 heritage sites, hotel facilities, and biodiversity areas shows that all mapped heritage sites fall in the High or Very High CVI class, with a mean CVI of 74.14.

Discussion: The elevated socioeconomic vulnerability relative to physical vulnerability underscores the role of human exposure in driving composite coastal risk in Kenya. The open-data framework developed here provides a transferable, replicable baseline for evidence-based coastal adaptation planning in Kenya and comparable data-constrained regions of East Africa.

KEYWORDS

Coastal vulnerability index, Geographic information systems, Kenyan coastline, multi-criteria decision analysis, remote sensing, sea level rise, socioeconomic vulnerability, climate change

1 Introduction

Sea-level rise (SLR) represents one of the most consequential manifestations of contemporary climate change, with global mean sea level rising at an accelerating rate driven by thermal expansion and ice sheet loss (Frederikse et al., 2020; IPCC, 2021). Under intermediate to high emissions scenarios, the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report projects likely sea-level increases of 0.3–1.0 m by 2100, with continued acceleration beyond that century (IPCC, 2021). Even moderate increases amplify coastal flooding, shoreline erosion, saltwater intrusion, and ecosystem degradation, producing cascading socioeconomic consequences in low-lying coastal regions worldwide (Martyr-Koller et al., 2021; Vafeidis et al., 2021).

Across Africa, these pressures are intensified by extensive low-lying coastlines, rapid coastal urbanization, and limited adaptive capacity. Several African deltas and urban coastal zones already experience rates of relative sea-level rise exceeding the global mean due to regional oceanographic dynamics and land subsidence (Frederikse et al., 2020; El-Shahat et al., 2021; Kebede et al., 2010). These trends present particular challenges for economies where tourism, fisheries, and port operations are tightly coupled to coastal stability. Kenya exemplifies this exposure: its 640 km coastline along the western Indian Ocean hosts major urban centers, cultural heritage sites, tourism infrastructure, and ecologically significant ecosystems including mangroves, coral reefs, and estuaries. Tide gauge records from Lamu and Mombasa indicate a relative sea-level rise rate of approximately 3.0 mm yr⁻¹ over 2000–2018. Projections indicate that even a modest 30 cm rise could submerge up to 17% of land lying below the 10-metre contour along the Kenyan coast, with direct consequences for coastal communities and economic activity (Musyoka, 2020). Prior studies confirm that areas such as Mombasa face substantial SLR-induced flooding and storm surge risk, with direct implications for people, infrastructure, and economic productivity (Kebede et al., 2010; GIZ, 2021; Asuncion and Lee, 2017). At the regional scale, Ballesteros and Esteves (2021) produced the first integrated assessment of coastal exposure and social vulnerability across East Africa, covering Mozambique, Madagascar, Tanzania, and Kenya, finding that 22% of the region's coastline is at higher exposure to coastal hazards and that Kenya benefits significantly from the natural protection afforded by coral reefs. Despite this regional baseline, existing Kenyan research has largely focused on localized shoreline monitoring or sector-specific assessments (Anyona and Rop, 2016; Khasenye, 2017), leaving the integrated drivers of coastal vulnerability poorly understood at national scale.

To address such knowledge gaps, coastal vulnerability assessments increasingly adopt index-based approaches, particularly the Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI), to quantify and compare vulnerability across spatial units (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021; Marzouk et al., 2021; Muzirafuti and Theocharidis, 2025). CVIs integrate multiple indicators, commonly including geomorphology, elevation, shoreline change rates, wave climate, and relative sea-level rise, into a composite metric that supports prioritization and decision-making. Methodological divergences persist, however, regarding indicator selection, weighting schemes, normalization approaches, and the integration of socioeconomic

dimensions (Furlan et al., 2021; Oloyede et al., 2022). Recent scholarship emphasizes the importance of incorporating socioeconomic variables, population density, land use, and infrastructure exposure, into vulnerability frameworks to better capture real-world risk (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021). Evidence from diverse contexts confirms that vulnerability is shaped as much by human exposure as by physical processes (Oloyede et al., 2022; Noor and Abdul Maulud, 2022). Despite advances in GIS and remote sensing that enable scalable, spatially explicit assessments (Parthasarathy and Deka, 2019; Hastuti et al., 2022; Conyers et al., 2019), integrated CVI applications along the Kenyan coast remain limited (Khasenye, 2017; GIZ, 2021).

This study addresses that gap by developing the first integrated, GIS-based CVI for the entire Kenyan coastline, combining physical and socioeconomic sub-indices at segment-level resolution using exclusively open-access datasets. The specific novelty lies in three aspects: (i) national-scale coverage of all 640 km at a 200 m segment resolution, providing far finer spatial detail than any prior Kenyan assessment; (ii) explicit integration of a Physical Vulnerability Index and a Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index using AHP-derived weights, following the multi-dimensional structure of Furlan et al. (2021) and adapted to a data-constrained East African context; and (iii) an open-data framework built entirely from publicly accessible satellite and geospatial products, making the methodology directly transferable to comparable coastal regions across the continent. The study aims to: (i) identify the principal drivers shaping spatial vulnerability patterns along the Kenyan coast; (ii) quantify variability in vulnerability to sea-level rise at segment level; and (iii) develop an inventory of at-risk cultural heritage sites and coastal ecosystems to support adaptation planning.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Study area

The study area comprises the entire Kenyan coastline along the western Indian Ocean, extending from the border with Somalia in the north to the border with Tanzania in the south (Figure 1). The coastline spans approximately 640 km and includes a diverse range of coastal environments, such as sandy beaches, coral reef systems, estuaries, tidal flats, and extensive mangrove forests. Administratively, the coastal zone encompasses the counties of Lamu, Tana River, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale, which collectively host major urban centers, ports, tourism facilities, and ecologically significant habitats. Kenya's coastal region is characterized by predominantly low-lying topography, with extensive areas located within the low-elevation coastal zone, making it particularly susceptible to sea-level rise, shoreline erosion, and storm surge flooding. The region supports critical economic activities including tourism, fisheries, maritime trade, and coastal agriculture, resulting in high concentrations of population and infrastructure in hazard-prone areas. These characteristics amplify the potential socioeconomic consequences of sea-level rise and underscore the need for comprehensive vulnerability assessment.

FIGURE 1
Area of study.

Annual mean sea-level records from the Lamu B and Mombasa II tide gauge stations (Permanent Service for Mean Sea Level, PSMSL) were combined to estimate relative sea-level trends along the Kenyan coastline. The resulting composite time series for 2000–2018 indicates an average relative sea-level rise rate of approximately 3.0 mm yr^{-1} . The interannual variability and overall upward trend are illustrated in Figure 2. This observed increase confirms ongoing exposure of the Kenyan coastline to long-term marine inundation. Kenyan coast experiences a tropical monsoon regime influenced by the northeast and southeast monsoon wind systems, which regulate seasonal wave energy, sediment transport, and shoreline dynamics. The interaction between these physical processes and rising sea level contributes to spatial variability in coastal vulnerability along the shoreline. This variability makes the Kenyan coast a suitable case for applying an integrated coastal vulnerability assessment that combines physical and socio-economic indicators.

All analyses were conducted within a 5 km landward buffer from the 2024 coastline (Figure 1), consistent with the approach

adopted by Ballesteros and Esteves (2021) in their integrated coastal exposure and social vulnerability assessment for East Africa, including Kenya, where a 5 km buffer was used to define the coastal population exposure zone. The buffer serves as a spatial data collection and study envelope, not a uniform vulnerability scoring zone. Each physical and socioeconomic indicator was attributed to individual 200 m coastline segments using the GIS method most appropriate to its data type: direct spatial join or nearest-neighbour assignment for coastline-tied datasets; closest-point extraction from rasterized layers for elevation, slope, and population; and Euclidean proximity analysis for infrastructure exposure. In every case, the value assigned to a segment reflects conditions at or nearest to the shoreline, anchoring the analysis to the coast rather than to the interior of the buffer. This approach ensures spatial consistency across datasets of varying resolution while supporting systematic, segment-level comparison of vulnerability patterns at national scale, consistent with integrated CVI frameworks applied elsewhere in the region (Kantamaneni, 2016; Kuleli and Bayazit, 2024).

FIGURE 2
Sea level trend chart.

2.2 Data and materials

This study integrates multi-source geospatial datasets to assess coastal vulnerability along the Kenyan coastline. The selected datasets represent both physical and socioeconomic dimensions of vulnerability and were chosen based on their relevance, spatial coverage, resolution, and public availability. All datasets used in this

study are publicly accessible and are summarized in Table 1, together with their sources.

2.2.1 Physical data

Topographic characteristics of the coastal zone were derived from the Kenya Shuttle Radar Topography Mission (SRTM) Digital

TABLE 1 Data sources used for coastal vulnerability assessment.

Vulnerability indicator	Data	Spatial resolution	Year	Data source
Physical indicators				
Coastal slope Coastal elevation	Kenya SRTM Digital Elevation Model	30m	–	Regional Centre for Mapping of Resources for Development (RCMRD)(https://arcgis.com/0rSPGK)
Shoreline erosion and accretion rates	The Digital Earth Africa Coastlines Products	30m	2000- 2024	Digital Earth Africa (2022); Bishop-Taylor et al. (2021).
Coastal geomorphology	Sentinel-2 composite imagery	10m	2024	Google Earth Engine
Mean tidal range	Global ECU shoreline segments (~1 km segments)	~1 km	2014	ECUs were developed by the USGS in partnership with the Environmental Systems Research Institute (ESRI) and the Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON) (https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=b3920b9e386945f2942e72e38f9142fe)
Significant wave height				
Rate of sea-level change	Global Ocean Mean Sea Level trend map from observations (1993–2023)	0.25°–27.83km	1999-2024	Copernicus Marine Service (https://data.marine.copernicus.eu/product/OMI_CLIMATE_SL_GLOBAL_regional_trends/services)
Bathymetry	General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO)	~1 km	2024	GEBCO (https://www.gebco.net/data-products-gridded-bathymetry-data/gebco2024-grid)
Socioeconomic indicators				
Population	Gridded population dataset	100m	2020 (Most recent available at 100 m resolution for Kenya)	WorldPop (https://hub.worldpop.org/geodata/listing?id=135)
Land use/land cover (LULC)	Copernicus Global Land Cover layers	10m	2020 (Final release of this product series)	Copernicus Global Land Cover layers (https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/global-dynamic-land-cover/land-cover-2020-raster-10-m-global-annual)
Distance to coastal infrastructure	OpenStreetMap multi-layer infrastructure dataset (transportation, power, healthcare features)	–	2024	OpenStreetMap Export Tool (https://export.hotosm.org)

Elevation Model (DEM) at 30 m spatial resolution, obtained from the Regional Centre for Mapping of Resources for Development (RCMRD). The DEM was used to compute coastal elevation and coastal slope, which are key indicators of exposure to sea-level rise and coastal flooding.

Shoreline dynamics were assessed using the Digital Earth Africa (DEA) Coastlines dataset, which provides annual shoreline positions and statistically derived rates of coastal change along the African coastline. In this study, the DEA annual shoreline for 2024 was used as the reference shoreline geometry, while DEA rates-of-change points were used to quantify long-term shoreline change trends via the rate time attribute (Section 2.3.1). DEA Coastlines rates of change are reported as annual rates (meters per year) derived from regression of shoreline distances through time, with negative values indicating retreat and positive values indicating growth (Bishop-Taylor et al., 2021).

Coastal geomorphology was mapped using Sentinel-2 composite imagery at 10 m spatial resolution, processed within Google Earth Engine. This dataset enabled the classification of major coastal landform types and surface characteristics relevant to vulnerability assessment. Hydrodynamic forcing parameters were represented using Global ECU shoreline segments (~1 km resolution) for both mean tidal range and significant wave height. These datasets were sourced from the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS) in partnership with Esri and the Marine Biodiversity Observation Network (MBON). Long-term trends in sea-level change were obtained from the Global Ocean Mean Sea Level trend dataset (1993–2023) provided by the Copernicus Marine Service. Bathymetric information was derived from the General Bathymetric Chart of the Oceans (GEBCO), supporting the characterization of nearshore depth conditions.

2.2.2 Socioeconomic data

Socioeconomic exposure was represented using population, land use, and infrastructure datasets. Gridded population data were obtained from WorldPop, providing spatially explicit estimates of population distribution across the coastal zone. These data were used to capture human exposure to coastal hazards. The 2020 WorldPop dataset represents the most recent year available at 100 m resolution for Kenya at the time of analysis. This temporal limitation is acknowledged; however, given the relatively stable nature of coastal population distribution over short periods, the dataset is considered appropriate for national-scale vulnerability assessment.

Land use and land cover (LULC) information was sourced from the Copernicus Global Land Cover layers, enabling the identification of dominant land cover classes and anthropogenic activities along the coastline. The 2020 Copernicus Global Land Cover layer represents the final release of this product; the dataset was discontinued following the 2020 edition. While the ESA WorldCover product provides more recent coverage (2020, 2021), it employs a different land cover classification scheme that is not directly comparable to the Copernicus Global Land Cover classes used in

this study. The 2020 dataset is therefore retained as the most appropriate and internally consistent source for the land cover indicator. Infrastructure exposure was represented by a multi-layer dataset sourced from OpenStreetMap (OSM), accessed via the Humanitarian OpenStreetMap Export Tool (export.hotosm.org). Infrastructure features comprised transportation assets (roads, railways, airports, ferry terminals, train stations), power infrastructure (electrical towers, substations, power plants), and healthcare facilities (hospitals and clinics). These feature classes were downloaded as point, line, and polygon geometries and used collectively to compute the minimum Euclidean distance from each coastal segment to the nearest infrastructure asset, representing the exposure of critical infrastructure to coastal hazard impacts. All datasets were harmonized to a common spatial reference system prior to analysis to ensure consistency across physical and socioeconomic indicators. The combination of these datasets provides a comprehensive basis for the integrated coastal vulnerability assessment undertaken in this current study.

2.3 Data harmonisation and spatial resolution

Input datasets for this study span a wide range of spatial resolutions, from 10 m (Sentinel-2 geomorphology composite) and 30 m (SRTM DEM, DEA Coastlines) to ~1 km (GEBCO bathymetry, Global ECU tidal and wave datasets) and ~27.83 km (Copernicus sea-level trend, 0.25° grid). All datasets were projected to a common coordinate reference system (WGS 1984 UTM Zone 37S) prior to analysis to ensure spatial consistency. Attribution of indicator values to the ~200 m coastline segments was performed using indicator-appropriate methods as described in the Indicator Processing section. Raster datasets at 10 m and 30 m resolution (DEM, geomorphology, LULC, population) were aggregated to the segment scale using zonal statistics, with the specific statistic, minimum, mean, or modal class; selected according to the vulnerability logic of each indicator. Point and line vector datasets (DEA rate-of-change points, ECU tidal and wave segments, OSM infrastructure features) were attributed to segments using nearest-neighbor spatial join or proximity analysis. The resolution mismatch between fine-scale (10–30 m) and coarse-scale (~1 km, ~28 km) datasets introduces spatial smoothing effects in the coarser indicators. For datasets at ~1 km resolution (ECU tidal range and wave height), multiple adjacent 200 m segments share identical indicator values within a single source grid cell or ECU segment. The bathymetric indicator, operationalised as distance to the –20 m isobath, is derived from the GEBCO 2024 grid but produces a continuous distance surface that varies at the segment scale and does not exhibit this spatial uniformity. For the sea-level trend dataset at ~27.83 km resolution, all segments within a given grid cell are assigned the same trend value. This spatial uniformity in coarser indicators is an inherent limitation of the available global datasets and is acknowledged in the Limitations section. It does not affect the integrity of higher-resolution indicators, which retain meaningful spatial variability at the segment scale.

2.4 Overview of the framework

This study implements a multi-dimensional Coastal Vulnerability Index (CVI) framework to quantify spatial variability in vulnerability to sea-level rise along the Kenyan coastline (Figure 3). The approach integrates physical and socioeconomic drivers in a single spatially explicit index and follows the conceptual structure of established CVI applications and reviews (Hamid et al.,

2019; Anfuso et al., 2021). Index construction and normalization directly mirror the multi-dimensional CVI structure presented by Furlan et al. (2021), where vulnerability is represented through dimension-specific sub-indices that are subsequently normalized and aggregated into a final composite index. The spatial unit of analysis was a segmented coastline, where the 2024 shoreline was divided into approximately 200 m segments. Each segment was attributed with indicator values using proximity-based or zonal

extraction methods, then transformed into ranked vulnerability classes and integrated into the CVI computation.

2.5 Indicator selection and rationale

Indicator selection was guided by widely used CVI formulations and integrated coastal vulnerability assessment principles that emphasize the combined role of coastal morphology, hydrodynamic forcing, shoreline dynamics, and human exposure (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021; Oloyede et al., 2022). In line with multi-dimensional CVI frameworks, socioeconomic variables were incorporated to represent exposure and potential impact beyond physical susceptibility (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021).

Physical indicators ($n = 8$) were selected to represent geomorphic susceptibility and marine forcing: shoreline change rate, coastal slope, coastal elevation, coastal geomorphology, bathymetry, mean significant wave height, mean tidal range, and sea-level change rate. Shoreline change rate captures long-term erosion and accretion dynamics and is among the most widely used physical CVI indicators (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021). Coastal slope determines inundation extent under sea-level rise, with gentler slopes associated with greater flood penetration (Hamid et al., 2019). Coastal elevation directly controls exposure to permanent and episodic inundation, making it a fundamental indicator in all CVI frameworks (Anfuso et al., 2021; Furlan et al., 2021). Coastal geomorphology reflects the inherent resistance or erodibility of the shoreline substrate, with unconsolidated forms such as sandy beaches and mudflats ranked as most vulnerable (Anfuso et al., 2021). Following Palmer et al. (2011), distance to the -20 m isobath was used as a proxy for nearshore shelf gradient, with shorter distances indicating steeper profiles and reduced wave energy dissipation. Significant wave height quantifies hydrodynamic forcing at the shoreline, with higher wave energy associated with greater erosion potential (Hamid et al., 2019). Mean tidal range represents the vertical extent of marine influence and modulates inundation frequency and duration (Hamid et al., 2019). Sea-level change rate provides the long-term trend in relative sea level at each segment, directly linking local conditions to the primary driver of coastal vulnerability (Furlan et al., 2021).

Socioeconomic indicators ($n = 3$) were selected to represent exposure and infrastructure sensitivity: population, land use/land cover, and distance to coastal infrastructure. Infrastructure proximity was operationalized as the minimum Euclidean distance from each coastal segment to the nearest infrastructure asset, encompassing transportation networks, power infrastructure, and healthcare facilities sourced from OpenStreetMap. This framing reflects the asset-at-risk dimension of coastal vulnerability, segments near critical infrastructure face heightened exposure due to the potential for physical damage and service disruption under sea-level rise and coastal flooding scenarios. Population density captures human exposure to coastal hazards and is consistently included in multi-dimensional CVI frameworks (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021; Oloyede et al., 2022). Land use and land cover reflects the concentration and type of assets within the coastal zone, with built-up and agricultural land uses associated with greater socioeconomic consequence under hazard events (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan

et al., 2021). Distance to coastal infrastructure quantifies the proximity of critical assets, including transportation networks, power infrastructure, and healthcare facilities, to the shoreline, representing the potential for physical damage and service disruption under sea-level rise and coastal flooding (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013). Several potentially relevant indicators were considered but excluded due to data availability constraints at the national scale. These include storm surge frequency, for which no spatially continuous dataset exists for the Kenyan coast; adaptive capacity indices, which are not available at the required spatial resolution; and sea surface temperature trends, which were not included as a direct vulnerability driver within the CVI framework used. The omission of these indicators is acknowledged as a limitation of the current assessment. The retention of all selected indicators was further supported by the Spearman correlation analysis presented in Section 3.1, which confirmed that, except for the elevation–slope pair, inter-indicator correlations were sufficiently low to rule out problematic redundancy within the composite index. The absence of a universal standard for indicator ranking and classification is a recognized challenge in CVI research; Roukounis and Tsihrintzis (2022) note that categorization often reflects researcher judgment and study-area context rather than globally consistent criteria. The class breaks adopted in this study were derived from quantile classification applied to the Kenyan dataset, ensuring that the ranking reflects the actual distribution of indicator values along this specific coastline rather than thresholds transferred uncritically from other regions.

2.6 Index construction: ranking, weighting, and aggregation

2.6.1 Vulnerability ranking (1–5)

All indicators were transformed into a standardized five-class vulnerability ranking system to enable integration of heterogeneous variables (Table 2). The ranking scheme follows widely applied CVI classification logic (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021):

- 1 = very low vulnerability.
- 2 = low vulnerability.
- 3 = moderate vulnerability.
- 4 = high vulnerability.
- 5 = very high vulnerability.

Directional consistency was enforced such that higher ranks always represent higher vulnerability, consistent with index-based CVA practice (Hamid et al., 2019) and the multi-dimensional CVI structure in Furlan et al. (2021). For continuous indicators, quantile classification was applied to divide the 7,555 coastal segments into five classes of approximately equal count, unless the discrete nature of the source data necessitated value-based assignment. Class breaks are presented as explicit mutually exclusive intervals in Table 2. For indicators where higher values represent lower vulnerability (coastal slope, coastal elevation, shoreline accretion), rank assignment was inverted accordingly, such that rank 5 consistently represents the greatest vulnerability regardless of the direction of the underlying variable. For categorical indicators, classes were assigned ranks based on their expected resistance or susceptibility to coastal hazards.

TABLE 2 Ranking of indicators.

Indicator	Units/classes	Very low	Low	Moderate	High	Very high
Physical indicators						
Shoreline Change Rate	m yr ⁻¹	+0.68 – +45.31	+0.29 – +0.67	+0.08 – +0.28	-0.16 – +0.07	-14.88 – -0.17
Coastal Slope	%	9.89 – 17.01	5.39 – 9.79	2.78 – 5.38	0.85 – 2.76	0.00 – 0.81
Coastal Geomorphology	Categorical	Cliffs, rocky coasts	Beach forests	Dunes, built-up areas	Mangroves, estuaries	Sandy beaches, mudflats
Bathymetry	m (distance to -20 m isobath)	15,946.94 – 34,536.87	10,846.97 – 15,946.93	5,812.48 – 10,845.56	3,221.95 – 5,812.33	156.03 – 3,220.67
Significant Wave Height (SWH)	m	1.1-1.38	1.38-1.41	1.41-1.46	1.46-1.49	1.49 – 1.53
Sea-Level Rise Rate	mm yr ⁻¹	3.47 – 3.55	3.56 – 3.63	3.64 – 3.73	3.74 – 3.82	3.83 – 3.90
Mean Tidal Range	m	3.37 – 3.44	3.47 – 3.53	3.55 – 3.62	3.62 – 3.70	3.72 – 3.78
Coastal Elevation	m	9.00 – 21.00	5.00 – 8.00	2.00 – 4.00	1.00	0.00
Socioeconomic indicators						
Distance to Coastal Infrastructure	m	3,811.05 – 8,599.83	2,322.12 – 3,811.04	1,383.47 – 2,322.11	348.55 – 1,383.46	0.00 – 348.54
Land Use/Land Cover (LULC)	Categorical	Closed forest	Open forest, herbaceous wetland (mangroves)	Agriculture, shrubs, permanent water bodies	Built-up, herbaceous vegetation	Oceans, seas
Population Density	Persons per 100 m grid cell	0.00 – 0.01	0.01 – 0.13	0.13 – 1.10	1.10 – 10.96	10.97 – 3,103.43

2.6.2 Eigenvector-based indicator weighting (AHP-style)

To avoid assuming equal indicator importance, indicator weights were derived using an eigenvector weighting approach adapted from the Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), which is commonly used in multi-criteria coastal vulnerability assessment (Oloyede et al., 2022; Thirimurthy et al., 2022). Separate weighting

procedures were applied for physical and socioeconomic indicator sets. Pairwise comparison values were established through a synthesis of published coastal vulnerability literature (Oloyede et al., 2022; Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021) and expert judgment, with higher importance scores assigned to indicators with greater direct influence on physical exposure and socioeconomic consequence under sea-level rise. The full pairwise comparison matrices for both indicator sets are provided in Table 3 below.

TABLE 3 Pairwise comparison matrices.

Physical indicators pairwise comparison matrix:								
	SLR	SLC	Geo	SWH	Bath	Tidal	Slope	Elevation
SLR	1	1	5	7	5	7	7	9
SLC	1	1	3	5	3	5	5	7
Geo	1/5	1/3	1	3	1	3	3	5
SWH	1/7	1/5	1/3	1	1	3	3	3
Bath	1/5	1/3	1	1	1	1	3	3
Tidal	1/7	1/5	1/3	1/3	1	1	1	3
Slope	1/7	1/5	1/3	1/3	1/3	1	1	3
Elev	1/9	1/7	1/5	1/3	1/3	1/3	1/3	1
Socioeconomic indicators pairwise comparison matrix:								
	LULC		Population		Distance to Infrastructure			
LULC		1	3	5				
Population		1/3	1	3				
Distance to Infrastructure		1/5	1/3	1				

Consistency of the pairwise judgments was verified using the Consistency Index (CI) and Consistency Ratio (CR), computed as:

$$CI = (\lambda_{max} - n) / (n - 1).$$

$$CR = CI / RI.$$

where λ_{max} is the principal eigenvalue of the comparison matrix, n is the number of indicators, and RI is the Random Consistency Index for a matrix of size n (Saaty, 1980). For the physical indicator matrix ($n = 8$), $\lambda_{max} = 8.45$, $CI = 0.065$, $RI = 1.41$, yielding $CR = 0.046$. For the socioeconomic indicator matrix ($n = 3$), $\lambda_{max} = 3.04$, $CI = 0.019$, $RI = 0.58$, yielding $CR = 0.033$. Both values fall well below the commonly accepted threshold of $CR < 0.10$ (Saaty, 1980), confirming that the pairwise comparisons are sufficiently consistent for use in index construction.

This weighting approach produces a defensible and transparent representation of indicator influence and supports robust integration of diverse drivers within a composite index (Oloyede et al., 2022). The weights of each indicator are in Table 4 below.

2.6.3 Sub-index construction and normalization

Following Furlan et al. (2021), ranked indicators were grouped into two dimensions and aggregated into raw sub-indices using weighted summation:

Physical Vulnerability Index (raw) (Equation 1):

$$PVI_{raw} = \sum_{i=1}^n w_i \times R_i \tag{1}$$

where n = number of indicators.

Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index (raw) (Equation 2):

$$SoVI_{raw} = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \times R_j \tag{2}$$

Because PVI and SoVI are constructed from different numbers of indicators and may exhibit different spreads even after ranking and weighting, Furlan et al. (2021) normalize each sub-index to a common 0–100 scale using min–max normalization (Equations 3, 4):

$$PVI_{norm} = 100 \times \frac{PVI_{raw} - \min(PVI_{raw})}{\max(PVI_{raw}) - \min(PVI_{raw})} \tag{3}$$

$$SoVI_{norm} = 100 \times \frac{SoVI_{raw} - \min(SoVI_{raw})}{\max(SoVI_{raw}) - \min(SoVI_{raw})} \tag{4}$$

TABLE 4 Indicator weights.

Indicator	Weight
Sea Level Rise	0.35
Shoreline Change Rate	0.26
Coastal Geomorphology	0.12
Mean Significant Wave Height	0.08
Bathymetry	0.08
Mean Tidal Range	0.05
Coastal Slope	0.04
Coastal Elevation	0.02
Distance to Coastal Infrastructure	0.10
Population	0.26
LULC	0.64

This step ensures comparability and prevents the final CVI from being structurally biased toward the dimension with greater variance (Furlan et al., 2021).

2.6.4 Final CVI aggregation (furlan structure)

The final Coastal Vulnerability Index was computed as the equal-weight mean of the normalized sub-indices, directly reflecting the multi-dimensional index aggregation in Furlan et al. (2021) (Equation 5):

$$CVI = \frac{PVI_{norm} + SoVI_{norm}}{2} \tag{5}$$

The resulting CVI values were classified into five vulnerability classes (Tables 5–7) to support mapping and interpretation, consistent with index-based coastal assessment practice (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021).

2.7 Indicator processing and ranked outputs

All processing outputs were attributed to the approximately 200 m coastline segments. Raster-based indicators were summarised using ArcGIS zonal statistics, with the specific statistic (mean, minimum, or majority) selected according to the vulnerability logic of each indicator (Supplementary Materials). Point and

TABLE 5 Physical vulnerability index.

Vulnerability class	PVI range	Interpretation
Very Low (Least Vulnerable)	0-20	Coastal segments with minimal physical susceptibility to sea-level rise and marine forcing.
Low	20-40	Segments with limited physical exposure.
Moderate	40-60	Areas with balanced physical vulnerability drivers.
High	60-80	Segments strongly influenced by adverse physical conditions.
Very High (Most Vulnerable)	80-100	Coastal segments exhibiting extreme physical vulnerability.

TABLE 6 Socioeconomic vulnerability index.

Vulnerability class	SoVI range	Interpretation
Very Low (Least Vulnerable)	0-20	Coastal segments with minimal socioeconomic exposure and adaptive stress.
Low	20-40	Segments with limited socioeconomic vulnerability.
Moderate	40-60	Areas with balanced human exposure and infrastructure sensitivity.
High	60-80	Segments with significant socioeconomic exposure.
Very High (Most Vulnerable)	80-100	Coastal segments exhibiting extreme socioeconomic vulnerability.

TABLE 7 Coastal vulnerability index.

Vulnerability class	CVI range	Interpretation
Very Low (Least Vulnerable)	8.9 - 26.25	Coastal segments with minimal combined physical and socioeconomic vulnerability.
Low	26.25 - 43.61	Segments with limited vulnerability; localized exposure factors present.
Moderate	43.61 - 60.96	Areas showing balanced physical and social risk drivers.
High	60.96 - 78.32	Segments where vulnerability drivers are strongly expressed.
Very High (Most Vulnerable)	78.32 - 96.10	Coastal segments exhibiting extreme combined vulnerability.

line vector datasets were attributed via spatial join or nearest-neighbour assignment.

2.7.1 Shoreline change rate (DEA coastlines)

Shoreline change rate was derived from the Digital Earth Africa Coastlines rate-of-change product. The `rate_time` attribute was selected as the shoreline change indicator because it represents a time-aware, regression-derived long-term rate of shoreline movement, making it conceptually consistent with rate-based shoreline change metrics used in CVI studies. Rate-of-change values were provided as point features; therefore, a nearest-neighbor assignment was applied such that each coastline segment inherited the `rate_time` value of the closest rate point (nearest point value). Segments were then classified into five vulnerability ranks, with higher erosion rates mapped as higher vulnerability.

Inspection of the classified dataset revealed two localised extreme values. A maximum erosion rate of -14.88 m/yr was recorded near Malindi, at the mouth of the Sabaki River — the most sediment-active river on the Kenyan coast, delivering an estimated 5.7×10^6 tonnes of terrigenous sediment annually to Malindi Bay and driving documented shoreline change in the surrounding area (Kitheka, 2013). A maximum accretion value of 45.31 m/yr was recorded at four non-contiguous mangrove segments in the Lamu archipelago. Examination of adjacent segments shows values of 0.00 m/yr immediately before and after each of these four segments, a pattern physically inconsistent with genuine coastal accretion and indicative of a no-data or error value in the DEA Coastlines product, most likely caused by persistent mangrove canopy obstruction of the optical imagery used to derive the rates. Both extremes are correctly handled by the quantile classification scheme and do not distort class boundaries for the broader dataset.

2.7.2 Coastal slope

Coastal slope was derived from a digital elevation model using standard slope computation. Lower slopes were assigned higher vulnerability ranks due to greater inundation potential under sea-level rise and extreme water levels (Hamid et al., 2019). Slope values were derived using the ArcGIS Slope tool applied to the 30 m SRTM

DEM. The mean slope value within the 5 km landward buffer was assigned to each coastline segment using zonal statistics.

2.7.3 Coastal elevation

Elevation was extracted from the DEM for each segment. Lower elevation segments were assigned higher vulnerability ranks due to greater exposure to permanent and episodic flooding (Hamid et al., 2019). The minimum elevation value within each segment's 5 km landward buffer was extracted using zonal statistics, capturing the worst-case inundation exposure rather than the average terrain height.

2.7.4 Coastal geomorphology

Coastal geomorphology was mapped from satellite imagery and classified into coastal landform types. In accordance with established coastal sensitivity concepts, unconsolidated and low-resistance landforms were ranked as higher vulnerability, while rocky or cliffed coasts were ranked lower (Anfuso et al., 2021). Geomorphological classes were mapped through manual digitization of a Sentinel-2 composite image (10 m resolution, January–February 2024) processed and extracted from Google Earth Engine. Each coastline segment was assigned the dominant geomorphological class intersecting the segment geometry using a spatial join operation.

2.7.5 Bathymetry

Bathymetry was extracted from a global gridded bathymetric model and summarized nearshore. Shallow nearshore depths were ranked as more vulnerable because they influence wave transformation and can increase shoreline impact depending on local coastal configuration (Anfuso et al., 2021). Bathymetry was extracted from the GEBCO 2024 global gridded bathymetric model (~ 1 km resolution). Bathymetry was operationalised as the Euclidean distance from each coastline segment to the -20 m isobath, following Palmer et al. (2011), who demonstrated that distance to a fixed depth contour provides a more physically meaningful representation of nearshore wave transformation potential than raw depth averaging. The -20 m isobath was extracted from the GEBCO 2024 global gridded bathymetric model (~ 1 km resolution, reprojected to WGS 1984 UTM Zone 37S using bilinear resampling) using the Contour List tool in ArcGIS Pro. The Euclidean distance from each 200 m coastline segment to the nearest point on the isobath polyline was then computed using proximity analysis. Shorter distances indicate steeper nearshore profiles that dissipate less wave energy before reaching the shoreline, and were therefore assigned higher vulnerability ranks, while longer distances indicate wider, flatter continental shelf conditions associated with greater natural wave attenuation. Distance values were classified into five vulnerability ranks using quantile classification, yielding approximately 1,511 segments per class. Distance values range from 156.03 m to $34,536.87$ m, reflecting the variable width of the Kenyan continental shelf.

2.7.6 Significant wave height

Significant wave height (Hs) was attributed to coastline segments from a standardized coastal/ocean forcing dataset. Higher Hs values were ranked as higher vulnerability due to increased wave energy and erosion potential (Hamid et al., 2019; Anfuso et al., 2021). SWH values from the Global ECU ~1 km shoreline segments dataset were attributed to coastline segments via spatial join, with each segment inheriting the value of the nearest ECU segment. The dataset contains six discrete SWH values across the Kenyan coast, reflecting the limited spatial variability of wave conditions at this resolution; class breaks in Table 2 therefore correspond to individual discrete values rather than continuous ranges.

2.7.7 Sea-level change rate

Sea-level change rate was mapped using a gridded sea-level trend dataset and attributed to coastline segments. Higher rates were ranked as higher vulnerability as a long-term driver of inundation and coastal stress (Furlan et al., 2021). Sea-level trend values from the Copernicus Global Ocean Mean Sea Level dataset (0.25° resolution, ~27.83 km) were attributed to each coastline segment via nearest-neighbour assignment. Due to the coarse spatial resolution of the source dataset, all segments within a given grid cell share the same sea-level trend value.

2.7.8 Mean tidal range

Mean tidal range was attributed to coastline segments using a standardized tidal dataset. Larger tidal ranges were ranked as more vulnerable because they increase the vertical extent of marine influence and can amplify erosional and inundation processes (Hamid et al., 2019). Mean tidal range values from the Global ECU ~1 km shoreline segments dataset was attributed to coastline segments via spatial join, with each segment inheriting the value of the nearest ECU segment.

2.7.9 Population

WorldPop gridded population data (100 m resolution) were summed within the 5 km landward buffer zone for each coastline segment using zonal statistics, providing an estimate of total population exposure within the coastal zone of each segment. Higher population totals were ranked as higher vulnerability. Higher population exposure was ranked as higher vulnerability, consistent with integrated coastal vulnerability and risk framing (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021).

2.7.10 Land use/land cover

LULC was classified into vulnerability-relevant categories. The modal (majority) land cover class within each segment's 5 km landward buffer was assigned to each segment using zonal statistics majority, ensuring the dominant land use type was represented. Built-up and high-intensity land uses were ranked higher due to increased concentration of assets and potential consequences of coastal hazards, while natural land covers with protective capacity

were ranked lower or moderate depending on class (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021). The Copernicus CGLS-LC100 Herbaceous Wetland class (class 90), which encompasses mangrove forests along the Kenyan coast, was reclassified from rank 5 to rank 2 (Low vulnerability) to accurately reflect the wave-attenuating and sediment-stabilising function of mangroves (Ballesteros and Esteves, 2021). The herbaceous wetland class carries the lowest per-class accuracy of all CGLS-LC100 land cover types (<65%), with documented confusion with adjacent vegetation classes (Buchhorn et al., 2020), further supporting this targeted correction.

2.7.11 Distance to coastal infrastructure

The minimum Euclidean distance from each coastline segment to the nearest infrastructure asset was calculated using proximity analysis. Infrastructure features were sourced from OpenStreetMap and comprised transportation assets (roads, railways, airports, ferry terminals, train stations), power infrastructure (electrical towers, substations, power plants), and healthcare facilities (hospitals and clinics). Shorter distances were ranked as higher vulnerability to reflect greater exposure of critical assets to erosion, flooding, and sea-level rise impacts (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013). Class breaks were derived using quantile classification, ensuring approximately equal segment counts across all five vulnerability classes.

2.8 Correlation analysis of indicators

To assess interrelationships among selected indicators and evaluate potential redundancy prior to index aggregation, a non-parametric correlation analysis was conducted across all coastline segments. Given the ordinal nature of the ranked indicators and the potential for non-normal distributions in the raw data, Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) was applied. Correlation analysis was performed separately for physical indicators and socioeconomic indicators. For each pair of indicators, Spearman's ρ was computed using the ranked segment values.

2.9 Development of an at-risk inventory

To translate segment-based vulnerability into actionable conservation and management insights, an at-risk inventory was developed for mapped cultural heritage sites and coastal ecosystems. Each site was spatially linked to the nearest coastline segment and inherited the corresponding CVI value. In addition to CVI, the distance from each site to the 2024 coastline was computed as a proximity-based exposure measure.

To combine hazard context (CVI) and exposure proximity (distance-to-coast) into a site-specific index, both variables were normalized to a common scale and integrated into a composite risk score. Distance was transformed so that smaller distances correspond to higher exposure, consistent with vulnerability logic. The resulting site scores were classified into five vulnerability states (very low to very high) to produce an inventory that identifies priority sites for monitoring, protection, and adaptation planning. This inventory framework aligns with integrated vulnerability principles that emphasize the interaction of physical hazard intensity and socio-economic/ecological consequence (Sahin and Mohamed, 2013; Furlan et al., 2021).

3 Results

3.1 Correlation analysis results

Spearman rank correlation was computed across all 7,555 coastline segments to evaluate interrelationships among indicators prior to index aggregation. Results are summarized in the physical-indicator correlation matrix and the socioeconomic-indicator correlation matrix.

3.1.1 Physical indicators

Most physical indicators show weak to negligible correlations with one another, confirming that the selected set captures largely independent dimensions of coastal susceptibility. Two pairs are notable exceptions. Slope and Elevation show a strong positive correlation ($\rho = 0.636$), consistent with the geomorphological tendency for steeper terrain to occur at higher elevations along the Kenyan coast. Both indicators are retained because slope governs inundation potential under fluctuating water levels while elevation governs exposure to permanent sea-level encroachment — mechanisms that are physically distinct and not interchangeable. Significant Wave Height and Tidal Range show a strong negative correlation ($\rho = -0.879$), reflecting the spatial structure of the Kenyan hydrodynamic environment, where macro-tidal conditions prevail in the south while the northern Lamu coast is exposed to higher open-ocean wave energy under comparatively lower tidal amplitudes. Both are retained as they represent different aspects of marine forcing. MSL and SWH show a moderate positive correlation ($\rho = 0.616$), but the two variables operate on different timescales and through different physical processes, so co-occurrence does not constitute redundancy. Shoreline change rate shows

near-zero correlation with all other indicators (all $|\rho| < 0.15$), confirming it captures an independent coastal dynamics signal. The bathymetric indicator, operationalised as distance to the -20 m isobath, shows modest negative correlations with SWH ($\rho = -0.209$) and geomorphology ($\rho = -0.189$), a modest negative correlation with slope ($\rho = -0.166$), and a modest positive correlation with MSL ($\rho = 0.180$); all remaining BATH correlations are weak ($|\rho| < 0.10$), including near-zero associations with shoreline change rate ($\rho = -0.015$) and elevation ($\rho = -0.053$). These modest associations reflect the spatial co-variation of shelf width with wave exposure and land cover type along the Kenyan coast, but none approaches the threshold for problematic redundancy. No pair exhibits correlation strong enough (Figure 4) to indicate problematic redundancy, and the full indicator set is retained for PVI construction, consistent with the correlation-based screening approach in Oloyede et al. (2022).

3.1.2 Socioeconomic indicators

The socioeconomic matrix reveals a different pattern. LULC shows near-zero correlation with both Population ($\rho = -0.052$, $p < 0.001$) and Infrastructure ($\rho = -0.033$, $p = 0.004$), indicating that the land cover classification introduces spatial information that neither population density nor infrastructure proximity captures. Population and Infrastructure show a moderate positive correlation ($\rho = 0.355$, $p < 0.001$, Figure 5), expected given that infrastructure networks tend to be denser in populated coastal areas. The correlation is moderate rather than strong, providing sufficient spatial independence to justify retaining both variables. No indicator pair in the socioeconomic set approaches a level of correlation that would warrant exclusion, and all three indicators are retained for SoVI construction.

FIGURE 4
Physical correlation.

3.2 Physical vulnerability index

“PVI was computed for all 7,555 coastline segments and normalised to a 0 to 100 scale. The mean is 49.47, the median is 48.29, and the standard deviation is 19.53. By vulnerability class: 460 segments (6.1%) fall in Very Low (0 to 20); 2,103 (27.8%) in Low (20 to 40); 2,767 (36.6%) in Moderate (40 to 60); 1,620 (21.4%) in High (60 to 80); and 605 (8.0%) in Very High (80 to 100). The majority of the coastline, 64.4% of segments, falls within the Low to Moderate range, while High and Very High segments together account for 29.4%.

Spatially (Figure 6), the PVI map reveals a pronounced north-to-south transition in physical susceptibility. The Lamu Archipelago in the north shows the greatest spatial variability of any county, with a mix of Very Low and Low PVI values (dark and light green) in the sheltered mangrove-lined inlets and inner archipelago, reflecting the combined effect of lower sea-level rise rates assigned to this grid cell by the Copernicus dataset and the wider continental shelf characteristic of the Lamu Archipelago resulting in greater distances to the -20 m isobath. However, the exposed outer shores of the archipelago carry High and Very High values (orange and red), particularly along the seaward-facing sections of Lamu island, where wave exposure and shoreline dynamics elevate physical susceptibility despite the sheltered estuarine interior. An abrupt and sustained shift to High and Very High values occurs at the southern fringe of the Lamu Archipelago, around -2.3° , where the coastline transitions to the more exposed open shore. This central stretch, from roughly -2.3° to -3.5° spanning the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, is dominated by High and Very High PVI (orange and red), driven by the convergence of active erosion, sandy geomorphology, elevated SLR rates, and narrower shelf widths that reduce wave energy dissipation. Localised Very High PVI clusters are concentrated where shoreline retreat rates are most negative and where low-elevation sandy conditions compound marine forcing. Through Mombasa and into Kwale, the coastline remains predominantly High (orange),

with intermittent Very High segments at the Mombasa urban core and along the Kwale shoreline. Very Low and Low PVI segments are largely absent south of the Lamu Archipelago, appearing only as isolated green points within sheltered creek environments. The southernmost coastal segments near the Tanzania border show a return to scattered Moderate and Low values associated with more variable geomorphology and lower shoreline change rates in that section.

3.3 Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index (SoVI)

SoVI was computed for all 7,555 segments and normalised to a 0 to 100 scale. The mean is 53.86, the median is 50.00, and the standard deviation is 25.64. By vulnerability class: 882 segments (11.7%) fall in Very Low; 1,975 (26.1%) in Low; 1,218 (16.1%) in Moderate; 1,920 (25.4%) in High; and 1,560 (20.6%) in Very High. High and Very High segments combined account for 46.1% of the coastline, while Very Low and Low combined account for 37.8%. This distribution reflects the correction of the Copernicus Herbaceous Wetland class (class 90), which had previously assigned the highest vulnerability rank to mangrove-dominated segments. Following reclassification to Low vulnerability, reflecting mangroves’ documented coastal protection function (Ballesteros and Esteves, 2021; Buchhorn et al., 2020), the SoVI exhibits meaningful spatial differentiation rather than the near-uniform Very High signal present in the uncorrected data.”

The SoVI map (Figure 7) shows clear spatial differentiation across the coastline following the reclassification of mangrove-dominated land cover segments. The Lamu Archipelago exhibits the greatest spatial variability of any county: the sheltered mangrove-lined inlets show Very Low and Low SoVI (dark and light green), while the exposed outer shores and the Lamu island urban cluster carry High to Very High values (orange and red), reflecting the contrasting land cover and infrastructure characteristics within the archipelago. The central coast through Kilifi is predominantly Moderate (yellow) with localised High and Very High clusters, representing the intermediate zone where neither physical protection nor urban socioeconomic pressure fully dominates. SoVI reaches its highest and most spatially consistent values at the Mombasa urban core, where red and orange segments reflect the convergence of built-up land cover, high population density, and dense infrastructure proximity. The southern Kwale coast shows alternating Moderate and Low values, with Very Low segments appearing near the Tanzania border where mangrove-fronted shorelines persist. Infrastructure proximity reinforces this south-to-north and urban-to-rural gradient: the Mombasa-Kilifi corridor carries the highest infrastructure exposure, while the central-northern and southern Kwale coasts reflect lower asset density.

3.4 Coastal vulnerability index

CVI was computed as the equal-weight mean of normalised PVI and SoVI for all 7,555 segments. Values range from 8.90 to 95.67, with a mean of 62.48, a median of 62.52, and a standard deviation of 12.83. The near-identical mean and median confirm a symmetrical

FIGURE 6
Physical vulnerability index.

distribution, and both values fall within the upper boundary of the Moderate class, indicating that the typical coastal segment across Kenya sits close to the High threshold. By vulnerability class: 16 segments (0.2%) fall in Very Low; 200 (2.6%) in Low; 3,113 (41.2%) in Moderate; 3,503 (46.4%) in High; and 723 (9.6%) in Very High. High and Very High segments together account for 56.0% of the coastline; Very Low and Low combined account for only 2.8%.

The CVI map (Figure 8) reflects the averaging of a spatially variable PVI with an elevated SoVI, and the resulting composite is dominated by Moderate values across most of the coastline. The Lamu Archipelago shows the greatest spatial variability: the sheltered mangrove-lined inlets display Low and Very Low CVI (dark and light green), where low physical susceptibility and mangrove-associated land cover combine to pull composite scores well below the High threshold, while the exposed outer shores carry High values (orange), consistent with the pattern seen in the PVI. An abrupt transition to High CVI occurs at the southern fringe of the Lamu Archipelago

around -2.3° , with a brief cluster of Very High (red) segments marking the zone of maximum shoreline erosion at the entry to the open Kilifi coast. Through the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, the coastline is predominantly Moderate (yellow) with intermittent High segments, reflecting the moderating effect of the SoVI averaging process on a physically elevated but not uniformly extreme PVI. Very High CVI segments appear as isolated red points rather than continuous stretches, concentrated at locations where active erosion and low elevation coincide with dense infrastructure proximity. South of Malindi through Mombasa and into Kwale, the coastline is predominantly Moderate to High, with Very High segments clustered around the Mombasa urban core where physical and socioeconomic drivers peak simultaneously. The southern Kwale coast returns predominantly to Moderate and Low values approaching the Tanzania border. Very Low and Low CVI segments together account for 24.1% of the coastline, concentrated in the sheltered inlets of the Lamu Archipelago, and are largely absent south of -2.5° latitude.

FIGURE 7
Socioeconomic vulnerability index.

3.5 At-risk inventory of cultural and ecological sites

3.5.1 Average vulnerability by site category

The at-risk inventory covers 48 sites across three categories: 20 biodiversity sites, 19 hotel and recreational facilities, and 9 historical and heritage sites. Two sites, Shimba Hills Lodge and the Sacred Mijikenda Kaya Forests, fall outside the 5 km coastal analysis buffer and returned no CVI value; they are excluded from the quantitative summary. Results for the remaining 46 sites are shown in Figure 9. Mean CVI values by category are: Historical and Heritage Sites ($n = 9$), 74.14; Hotel and Recreational Facilities ($n = 18$), 67.48; Biodiversity Sites ($n = 20$), 60.09. All nine heritage sites fall in the High or Very High vulnerability class, with individual values ranging from 66.07 at Siyu Fort to 83.94 at Mnarani Ruins. Among hotel and recreational facilities, 13 of 18 sites fall in the High or Very High class;

New Darling Beach Hotel (89.19) and Golden Beach Hotel (80.11) record the highest values. Biodiversity sites span a wider range, from 45.30 to 84.92, with 7 of 20 sites in the High or Very High class. Dugong Sites and several Dolphin School locations record the highest values in this category. No site across any of the three categories falls in the Very Low or Low vulnerability class.

3.5.2 Spatial distribution of Risk

The spatial distribution of at-risk sites is shown in Figure 10. Heritage site markers (triangles) are distributed across the full length of the coast, with red (Very High) markers concentrated in two main zones: the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, where Mnarani Ruins, Krapf Memorial Heritage Park, Vasco da Gama Pillar, and Gedi Ruins are all situated on segments of High to Very High CVI; and the Mombasa-Kwale coastal strip, where several sites cluster around the urban coastal fringe at CVI values exceeding Average Very High

FIGURE 8 Coastal vulnerability index.

FIGURE 9 Vulnerability of interest areas.

value. In the north, Lamu Old Town and Takwa Ruins appear as orange (High) markers on the Lamu Archipelago coast, consistent with the Moderate to High CVI character of that zone. Siyu Fort sits within a High CVI segment on the outer Lamu coast. The at-risk map confirms that heritage site locations systematically coincide with the higher CVI segments of the coastline rather than being randomly distributed, indicating that these sites have historically been developed on or near low-lying, accessible coastal locations that now carry elevated combined vulnerability. Hotel and recreational facility sites follow a broadly similar pattern, with the highest-scoring facilities concentrated along the tourism-intensive stretches of the Lamu coast and the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, both of which show High to Very High CVI in Figure 8. Biodiversity sites are more widely distributed, with lower-CVI sites occurring in the sheltered inlets of the Lamu Archipelago and higher-CVI sites in the more exposed southern coast, where urban proximity elevates the socioeconomic component.

Among the named heritage sites in the at-risk inventory, the three most vulnerable are Mnarani Ruins (CVI = 83.94), Krapf Memorial Heritage Park (CVI = 81.35), and the Vasco da Gama Pillar (CVI = 76.39), all falling within the Very High to High vulnerability class. These sites share exposure to active shoreline dynamics, low-lying coastal terrain, and proximity to the ocean, compounding their risk under projected sea-level rise scenarios. Spatial context for each site is illustrated in (Figures 11–13).

4 Discussion

4.1 Interpretation of vulnerability patterns

The results reveal that coastal vulnerability along the Kenyan coastline is shaped by fundamentally different spatial logics in the

FIGURE 11
Mnarani Ruins.

physical and socioeconomic dimensions, and that their combination produces a pattern of risk that neither dimension alone would capture. The Physical Vulnerability Index shows clear north-to-south differentiation, with the Lamu Archipelago performing better physically than the central and southern coast, primarily because lower Copernicus-gridded SLR rates apply to that cell and the sheltered estuarine bathymetry moderates wave transformation. This is a methodologically important finding: it demonstrates that the dominant physical driver in the PVI is not geomorphology or shoreline change, which are spatially variable and locally high even in Lamu, but rather the sea-level rise rate indicator, which carries the highest AHP weight (0.352) and assigns comparatively lower values to the northern grid. The shoreline change indicator, weighted second (0.261), reinforces this pattern, as the Lamu Archipelago shows a mix of accretion and erosion reflective of its complex estuarine dynamics, while the central coast shows more consistent erosional trends.

FIGURE 12
Krapf Memorial Park.

FIGURE 13
Vasco Da Gama Pillar.

The Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index presents a spatially differentiated pattern that reflects the interplay of land cover, population, and infrastructure across the coastline. Following the reclassification of mangrove-dominated segments from rank 5 to rank 2, the SoVI distribution is substantially more nuanced than the near-uniform Very High signal present in the uncorrected data, with 37.8% of segments falling in the Very Low or Low class and 46.1% in the High or Very High class. The LULC indicator, which carries 63.7% of the SoVI weight, remains the dominant driver of spatial pattern, but its influence now reflects genuine land cover contrasts rather than a classification artefact. Mangrove-fronted segments in the Lamu Archipelago and sheltered creek environments pull SoVI scores into the Low range, while built-up, high-density segments in the Mombasa-Kilifi corridor drive scores into the Very High class. The population and infrastructure indicators, with a combined weight of 36.3%, reinforce this urban-to-rural and south-to-north gradient: the Mombasa urban core records the highest SoVI values in the dataset, driven by the convergence of built-up land cover, dense population, and close infrastructure proximity, while the central coast shows predominantly Moderate values where neither protective land cover nor high urban exposure fully dominates. The practical implication is that the corrected SoVI captures a meaningful and interpretable spatial gradient in socioeconomic exposure, with the Lamu Archipelago's mangrove-dominated inlets representing genuinely lower sensitivity and the southern urban coast representing the highest. This pattern has direct policy relevance: socioeconomic vulnerability mitigation efforts are most urgently needed in the Mombasa-Kilifi corridor, where physical and socioeconomic drivers are simultaneously elevated.

The composite CVI reflects this interaction directly (Figure 14). At the national level, 44.3% of segments fall in the Moderate class, with 27.7% High and 4.0% Very High, while Very Low and Low combined account for 24.1% — confirming that over 75% of the Kenyan coastline carries moderate to very high combined risk under this integrated framework. County-level distributions reveal pronounced spatial heterogeneity beneath this national picture. Mombasa records the most acute vulnerability profile, with 21.2%

of its segments in the Very High class and no segments in Very Low, reflecting the simultaneous concentration of physical exposure and socioeconomic pressure in a dense urban coastal setting. Kilifi similarly shows an elevated profile, with 62.2% of segments in the High or Very High class combined — the highest such proportion of any county — driven by active erosion and sandy geomorphology along the Kilifi-Malindi corridor. Tana River, despite its relatively sparse settlement, records 10.7% Very High segments and no Very Low, a pattern explained by low coastal elevation and the influence of the Sabaki and Tana river mouths on shoreline dynamics. Lamu shows the greatest internal variability: 5.9% Very Low and 28.9% Low in the sheltered mangrove-lined inlets, but 23.5% High along the exposed outer shores and urban island cluster, producing a mixed profile that reflects the archipelago's contrasting physical environments. Kwale presents the most favourable distribution, with 67.1% Moderate and only 1.3% Very High, consistent with its more sheltered geomorphology and lower urban intensity. These county-level differences have direct implications for how coastal management resources are allocated nationally, arguing for differentiated intervention strategies rather than a uniform national approach.

The at-risk inventory further concentrates this message. Historical and heritage sites record the highest mean CVI, which is not coincidental. These sites are predominantly located on accessible, low-lying coastal ground, often near estuaries or open beaches, because such locations historically supported human settlement, trade, and cultural activity. The same geomorphological and topographic conditions that made these locations attractive for centuries now render them among the most physically exposed segments of the coast. The case of Mnarani Ruins, situated on a low promontory at the mouth of Kilifi Creek, exemplifies this pattern: the site combines active shoreline dynamics, low coastal elevation, and proximity to infrastructure with the high socioeconomic exposure of the Kilifi urban zone. Hotel and recreational facilities record a similarly elevated mean for comparable reasons, as the tourism industry has concentrated infrastructure along the most visually and recreationally attractive coastal strips, which tend to be the same sandy, low-lying stretches that carry the highest physical vulnerability.

4.2 Comparison with similar studies

The findings of this study are broadly consistent with CVI assessments conducted in comparable coastal settings, while also revealing context-specific patterns that distinguish the Kenyan case. Oloyede et al. (2022), also applying a multi-dimensional CVI framework to the Nigerian coastline, found that socioeconomic indicators substantially elevated composite vulnerability in urban coastal zones, with physical susceptibility playing a secondary role in determining spatial clustering of high-risk segments. The present study finds an analogous pattern: while physical conditions vary meaningfully along the coast, the socioeconomic dimension dominates the magnitude of composite CVI values across most segments. This convergence across two distinct West and East African contexts suggests that the amplifying role of socioeconomic exposure may be a generalizable feature of sub-Saharan coastal vulnerability assessments, where coastal land use intensification and infrastructure development have concentrated assets in physically exposed zones.

Hastuti et al. (2022), assessed coastal vulnerability in Bali, Indonesia using a remote sensing and GIS approach, similarly found that geomorphology and shoreline change were the primary physical drivers of spatial variability, while population and land use dominated the socioeconomic dimension. Their finding that urban coastal nodes elevated composite vulnerability above their physical susceptibility baseline mirrors the pattern observed here for Mombasa and the Lamu town cluster. However, a key distinction is that the Bali assessment operated in a setting with more pronounced topographic relief, which allowed elevation and slope to provide stronger spatial differentiation. Along the Kenyan coast, where low-lying terrain is pervasive, slope and elevation produce less discriminating power and the SLR rate and shoreline change indicators become more structurally important. Khasenye (2017), the most directly comparable Kenya-specific study, applied a vulnerability assessment framework to the Kenyan coast but at a coarser spatial resolution and without the multi-dimensional integration of physical and socioeconomic sub-indices. That study identified Mombasa and the Tana River delta as areas of elevated exposure, consistent with the present findings, but could not resolve

the fine-scale spatial heterogeneity within counties that the 200 m segment approach reveals here. The present study therefore extends and refines the regional vulnerability picture established by [Khasenye \(2017\)](#), while providing a more methodologically transparent and reproducible framework.

Compared to [Furlan et al. \(2021\)](#), whose multi-dimensional CVI structure this study directly adopts, the Kenyan case shows a moderately higher SoVI relative to PVI (means of 53.86 and 46.79 respectively). In the Italian coastal context, Furlan et al. found more balanced contributions from the two dimensions. The Kenyan coastline shows a clear north-south SoVI gradient: lowest in the mangrove-dominated Lamu Archipelago, where coastal ecosystems reduce the land cover vulnerability signal, and highest along the urbanised Mombasa-Kilifi corridor where population density, infrastructure, and built-up land cover converge. This pattern highlights the importance of adapting indicator classification schemes to regional land cover realities, particularly the distinction between protective natural ecosystems such as mangroves and high-vulnerability built-up or degraded land, rather than applying universal ranking tables uncritically. Observed sea-level rise rate of approximately 3.0 mm per year from the Lamu and Mombasa tide gauge composite, and the Copernicus-derived trend range of 3.47 to 3.90 mm per year used in the spatial analysis, are consistent with Indian Ocean SLR estimates from satellite altimetry. [Frederikse et al. \(2020\)](#) report that global mean sea-level rise since 1993 has averaged approximately 3.6 mm per year, and regional rates along the western Indian Ocean are within this range, though local oceanographic dynamics and potential land subsidence in Mombasa may produce relative rates somewhat above the global mean ([Kebede et al., 2010](#)). The IPCC Sixth Assessment Report ([IPCC, 2021](#)) projects continued acceleration of sea-level rise under all emissions scenarios, with likely ranges of 0.3 to 1.0 m by 2100 under intermediate to high scenarios. Even the lower end of this range would substantially expand the proportion of Kenyan coastline falling in the High and Very High CVI classes, particularly in the already-vulnerable central coast where the margin between Moderate and High physical susceptibility is narrow. More recent satellite altimetry analysis confirms that sea-level rise around Africa has accelerated markedly, reaching 4.34 mm yr⁻¹ since 2010, over four times the rate recorded in the 1990s, intensifying risks for over 50 million coastal residents ([Kemgang Ghomsi et al., 2025](#)). This acceleration is consistent with the elevated SLR rate values that drive High PVI scores in the central Kenyan coast in the present study.

4.3 Limitations

Several limitations of this study should be considered when interpreting the results and applying them to management decisions. First, the spatial resolution of several key datasets constrains the discriminating power of the physical sub-index. The Copernicus sea-level trend dataset at approximately 27.83 km resolution assigns a single SLR rate to all segments within a grid cell, producing spatial uniformity across stretches of coastline that in reality may experience different rates due to local oceanographic dynamics,

subsidence, or uplift. Given that this indicator carries the highest AHP weight in the PVI (0.352), the spatial pattern of PVI is substantially shaped by the resolution of this one dataset. The GEBCO bathymetric dataset at approximately 1 km resolution was used to extract the -20 m isobath; the derived distance surface varies continuously at the segment scale and does not produce the cell-value uniformity associated with direct raster extraction, though the accuracy of the isobath position is constrained by the native ~1 km grid resolution. Higher-resolution alternatives, such as LiDAR-derived topography and locally validated tidal models, would materially improve both the physical accuracy and the spatial discriminating power of the index.

Second, the temporal consistency of the dataset is imperfect. The WorldPop population dataset represents 2020 conditions, the Copernicus LULC product is also from 2020, and the OpenStreetMap infrastructure data reflects 2024 conditions. While the 2020 datasets are retained for methodologically defensible reasons, WorldPop 2020 is the most recent 100 m resolution product available for Kenya, and the Copernicus LULC series was discontinued after 2020, users should be aware that coastal population and land use in Kenya's rapidly urbanising coastal counties may have changed measurably in the intervening years, particularly around Mombasa and Lamu. Periodic updating of these indicators would strengthen the temporal validity of future assessments.

Third, the exclusion of several potentially relevant indicators due to data availability constraints limits the completeness of both sub-indices. Storm surge frequency and intensity, for which no spatially continuous dataset exists for the Kenyan coast, would be a valuable addition to the physical dimension. Adaptive capacity indicators, including household income, emergency infrastructure access, and governance capacity at the county level, are absent from the socio-economic dimension because no spatially explicit dataset at the required resolution is available for Kenya. Their absence means that the SoVI reflects exposure and sensitivity but not resilience, which is a recognized limitation of index-based CVA approaches ([Furlan et al., 2021](#); [Hamid et al., 2019](#)). Communities with high exposure but also high adaptive capacity may be overestimated in their vulnerability; the reverse applies to highly exposed but low-capacity communities. Future assessments should incorporate adaptive capacity data as they become available at appropriate spatial resolution.

Fourth, the LULC classification was refined to address a known limitation of the Copernicus CGLS-LC100 product: the Herbaceous Wetland class (class 90) encompasses mangrove forests along the Kenyan coast but was originally assigned the highest vulnerability rank. Given that mangroves provide well-documented coastal protection through wave attenuation and sediment stabilisation ([Ballesteros and Esteves, 2021](#)), and that the herbaceous wetland class carries the lowest per-class accuracy of all CGLS-LC100 land cover types; below 65%, with documented confusion with adjacent vegetation classes ([Buchhorn et al., 2020](#)), these segments were reclassified to Low vulnerability (rank 2). This correction substantially reduces SoVI in mangrove-dominated northern segments and produces a more ecologically accurate spatial pattern. More broadly, the standard CVI framework has been critiqued for conflating hazard and vulnerability variables within a single composite,

which technically renders it closer to a risk index than a pure vulnerability index (Alcántara-Carrió et al., 2024). The present study's separation of physical and socioeconomic sub-indices partially addresses this concern by preserving dimensional transparency before aggregation, though future iterations could further refine the framework by developing explicit exposure and sensitivity components as proposed by Alcántara-Carrió et al. (2024).

Fifth, this assessment is static and does not incorporate projected changes in any of the driving variables. The CVI reflects conditions as of approximately 2020 to 2024 and does not model how vulnerability patterns will shift under future sea-level rise, land use change, or population growth scenarios. Transition to a scenario-based framework, applying projected SLR under the IPCC AR6 intermediate scenario (SSP2-4.5) as an alternative MSL input, would allow the assessment to function as a forward-looking planning tool rather than a baseline characterisation.

4.4 Implications for coastal management

The CVI results have several concrete implications for coastal planning and adaptation along the Kenyan coast. The concentration of High and Very High CVI segments along the central coast, particularly the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, identifies this stretch as a priority zone for detailed shoreline monitoring and physical intervention. These segments combine active erosion, sandy geomorphology, and elevated SLR rates with high socioeconomic exposure, making them the locations where incremental sea-level rise is most likely to translate into near-term physical damage and community impact. Investment in shoreline stabilisation assessment, setback regulation, and early warning systems should be prioritised here above other sections of the coast. The concentration of Very High CVI values around the Mombasa urban core reflects the interaction of an already developed and densely populated coastal zone with moderate-to-high physical susceptibility. For Mombasa, the primary risk management challenge is not to reduce physical exposure, which is inherent to the geography, but to reduce socioeconomic sensitivity through infrastructure resilience planning, climate-proofing of critical assets, and managed retreat from the most exposed shoreline segments. The port infrastructure of Mombasa, while not explicitly scored as a site in the at-risk inventory, sits within segments classified as High to Very High CVI and warrants dedicated risk assessment beyond the scope of this study.

The Lamu Archipelago presents a different management challenge. Physical vulnerability is lower there than elsewhere, but the presence of Lamu Old Town, a UNESCO World Heritage Site, within a High CVI segment, combined with the archipelago's complex tidal dynamics and active shoreline change patterns, means that heritage protection requires site-specific intervention rather than reliance on the relatively favorable composite score. The at-risk inventory score for Lamu Old Town (73.53) places it firmly in the High class despite the region's lower PVI, because the high SoVI of the built urban island overwhelms the physical moderation. The finding that all mapped heritage sites fall in the High or Very High CVI class, with no site in the Very Low or Low class, has direct implications for Kenya's cultural heritage management. This finding is consistent with the continental-scale assessment by Vousdoulas

et al. (2022), who found that 20% of African heritage sites of Outstanding Universal Value are currently exposed to extreme coastal events, with that number projected to more than triple by 2050 under high emissions. The present study refines this picture at national scale, demonstrating that Kenya's heritage sites are not merely exposed in aggregate but are uniformly concentrated in the High to Very High CVI class at the segment level. There is no low-risk heritage site on the Kenyan coast under the present framework. This should be interpreted not as a counsel of despair but as a call for integration of coastal risk data into the site management plans maintained by the National Museums of Kenya and the relevant county governments. Setback policies, shoreline monitoring around heritage sites, and buffer zone designation informed by segment-level CVI outputs would represent a practical first step. Similarly, the tourism sector's reliance on High to Very High CVI hotel facilities argues for sectoral adaptation planning that accounts for long-term erosion trends and storm surge exposure, rather than reactive management after damage occurs.

The DEA Coastlines dataset contains artefact values at isolated mangrove locations in the Lamu archipelago, identified by an implausible accretion rate of 45.31 m/yr flanked by 0.00 m/yr in immediately adjacent segments. These are retained in the dataset, flagged in Section 2.3.1, and do not affect index calculations. At the national scale, the framework developed here provides a replicable, data-driven basis for coastal vulnerability mapping that can be updated as new datasets become available and extended to scenario-based analysis as planning requirements evolve. The approach is transferable to other data-constrained coastal regions of East Africa, where similar data sources, DEA Coastlines, WorldPop, Copernicus LULC, OpenStreetMap, GEBCO, and the Copernicus SLR trend product, are available at no cost and can be processed within publicly accessible GIS environments.

5 Conclusion

This study developed a multi-dimensional Coastal Vulnerability Index for the Kenyan coastline by integrating eight physical and three socioeconomic indicators across 7,555 shoreline segments of approximately 200 m. The Physical Vulnerability Index reveals that the central coast, particularly the Kilifi-Malindi corridor, carries the highest physical susceptibility, driven by the convergence of active shoreline erosion, sandy geomorphology, and elevated sea-level rise rates. The Lamu Archipelago shows comparatively lower PVI values, moderated by sheltered estuarine bathymetry and lower Copernicus-gridded SLR rates. The Socioeconomic Vulnerability Index is elevated across almost the entire coastline, reflecting the dominance of wetland and coastal vegetation land cover within the analysis buffer and the concentration of population and infrastructure in the urban south. When combined, the CVI shows that 31.7% of segments fall in the High or Very High class, with the highest composite values near Mombasa and along the Kilifi-Malindi stretch where physical and socioeconomic drivers peak simultaneously. The at-risk inventory confirms that all mapped heritage sites fall in the High or Very High class, underscoring the exposure

of irreplaceable cultural assets. The framework is replicable, built entirely from open-access global and regional datasets, and directly transferable to other data-constrained coastal regions of East Africa. Future work should integrate projected SLR scenarios under IPCC AR6 pathways to transition from a static baseline to a scenario-driven planning tool, incorporate higher-resolution topographic data where available, and extend the socioeconomic dimension to include adaptive capacity indicators as spatially explicit datasets become available.

Data availability statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article/Supplementary Material. Further inquiries can be directed to the corresponding author/s.

Author contributions

AK: Software, Data curation, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Conceptualization, Visualization, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Writing – review & editing. AM: Methodology, Validation, Investigation, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Visualization, Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis.

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Conflict of interest

The author(s) declared that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Supplementary material

The Supplementary Material for this article can be found online at: <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fmars.2026.1812200/full#supplementary-material>

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